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Nasarawa State University Journal of Special and Inclusive Education (NSUJSIE)

ISSN: 3121-729X

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Teachers' Attitude and Competence as Determinants of Inclusive Service Delivery for Pupils with Intellectual Disability in Cross River State, Nigeria

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Citation: Ataben, M. O., & Iroham, N. S. (2026). Teachers' attitude and competence as determinants of inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disability in Cross River State, Nigeria. *Nasarawa State University Journal of Special & Inclusive Education*, 1(1), 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19398146>

Academic Editor: Dr. Jummai Jerry

Received: 14 November, 2025
Revised: 8 December, 2025
Accepted: 3 February, 2026
Published: 1 April, 2026

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Abstract: *This study investigated teachers' attitudes and competence as determinants of inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in Cross River State (CRS), Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, the researchers raised two research questions and two null hypotheses to guide the study. Employing a correlational survey, this study used a researcher-developed and validated questionnaire, the 'Determinants of Inclusive Service Delivery Questionnaire (DISDQ)', to collect data. Researchers selected a sample of 12,749 primary school teachers in CRS from the study population of all primary school teachers in Cross River State. Simple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. Study results revealed a correlation between inclusive service delivery and teacher attitudes; however, teachers' competence does not contribute to inclusive service delivery in the study area. From the results, it was concluded that teachers' attitude and competence determine inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in the study area. Among other things, the study recommended that teachers engage in continuous professional development to update their knowledge and skills in providing inclusive services for pupils with intellectual disabilities.*

Keywords: Teachers' attitude, Teachers' competence, Inclusive service, Intellectual disability

Introduction

Inclusive education has emerged globally as a rights-based and equity-driven reform agenda aimed at dismantling systemic barriers that restrict access, participation, and achievement for learners with disabilities. Rather than merely serving as a placement model, inclusive education represents a transformative framework that restructures school cultures, policies, and practices to accommodate learners' diversity within mainstream classrooms. At its core, inclusive education promotes social justice, equal opportunity, and non-discrimination. It ensures that neighbourhood schools educate learners with disabilities alongside their peers without disabilities.

In Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Education formally institutionalised this philosophy through the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2023). The policy emphasises equitable access, participation, curriculum flexibility, individualised support, and collaborative service delivery for learners with disabilities (pupils with intellectual disabilities inclusive). The policy aligns with international commitments such as inclusive schooling frameworks and Sustainable Development Goals, which advocate “education for all” and appear progressive; the translation of inclusive ideals into classroom realities remains uneven and context dependent. In several states, including Cross River State, infrastructural deficits, overcrowded classrooms, inadequate instructional materials, limited specialist support, and insufficient teacher preparation undermine the effective implementation of inclusive service delivery.

Empirical evidence consistently demonstrates that inclusive educational settings offer significant benefits when appropriately implemented. Learners with disabilities educated alongside their non-disabled peers often exhibit improved academic performance, enhanced communication skills, greater social integration, and stronger self-esteem (Sermier et al., 2017). Inclusion also benefits non-disabled learners by fostering empathy, collaboration, diversity acceptance, and pro-social behaviour. However, the realisation of these outcomes is heavily contingent upon teacher-related variables, particularly attitudes and competence.

The American Association on Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities (2021) defines intellectual disability as a condition characterised by significant limitations in intellectual functioning and adaptive behaviour, originating before the age of 18 years. Intellectual functioning includes reasoning, learning, and problem-solving abilities, while adaptive behaviour encompasses conceptual, social, and practical life skills required for everyday functioning. Pupils with intellectual disabilities may experience challenges in academic learning pace, memory retention, communication, self-care, and social judgment. As observed by Ataben, Udie, and Adimabua, (2025), although cognitive growth may be slower among this population, environmental supports and instructional quality can significantly influence developmental trajectories. Thus, educational outcomes are not solely determined by the disability itself but also by the responsiveness of the learning environment.

Within inclusive classrooms, teachers function as the principal agents of policy enactment and pedagogical transformation. Their perceptions, expectations, and professional capabilities directly influence whether inclusion becomes meaningful participation or superficial integration. Teachers' attitudes toward inclusion reflect their beliefs about the feasibility, desirability, and practicality of educating pupils with intellectual disabilities in mainstream settings. These attitudes are multidimensional, encompassing cognitive (beliefs and knowledge), affective (emotions and feelings), and behavioural (intentions and actions) components. Research indicates that teachers who perceive inclusion as beneficial and manageable are more likely to employ differentiated instruction, collaborative strategies, and supportive classroom management techniques (Klibthong, 2016; Classen & Westbrook, 2020). Conversely, negative attitudes often manifest as resistance, lowered expectations, reluctance to adapt instruction, or preference for segregated placement.

In the Nigerian context, findings on teacher attitudes toward inclusive education remain mixed and sometimes contradictory. Ugo and Yakwal (2017) documented predominantly negative attitudes among primary school teachers toward inclusion of learners with visual impairment in Plateau State, attributing such dispositions to inadequate training and lack of institutional support. In contrast, other studies suggest that exposure to inclusive training, prior experience with learners with disabilities, and administrative encouragement positively influence teachers' attitudes (Ajuwon, 2020; Akinwumi et al., 2024). These variations underscore the importance of examining contextual determinants of teacher disposition within specific states, such as Cross River.

While attitude is crucial, positive disposition alone does not guarantee effective practice. Teacher competence represents the operational dimension of inclusive education. Competence in inclusive settings extends beyond general pedagogical skill; it involves specialized knowledge of learner diversity, curriculum differentiation, instructional scaffolding, formative assessment adaptation, behaviour intervention strategies, individualized educational planning, and collaboration with parents and support professionals. Competent teachers can modify content, adjust instructional pace, utilise multisensory teaching approaches, implement universal design for learning principles, and manage heterogeneous classrooms effectively.

Darling-Hammond (2017) and Darling-Hammond, Hyler, and Gardner (2017) emphasise that high-quality teaching relies on integrated professional knowledge, sustained training, and reflective practice. In inclusive contexts, competence also requires ongoing professional development, mentoring, and institutional backing. Without adequate competence, even teachers with favourable attitudes may struggle to translate inclusive intentions into effective classroom practice. Conversely, technically skilled teachers who lack positive attitudes may implement strategies mechanically without fostering genuine inclusion. This suggests a possible interactive or joint influence of attitude and competence on inclusive service delivery.

Inclusive service delivery itself entails the systematic provision of instructional, social, and behavioural supports that enable pupils with intellectual disabilities to access, participate in, and benefit from the general education curriculum. It encompasses curriculum adaptation, individualised goal setting, inclusive assessment practices, classroom accommodations, peer-mediated strategies, and collaborative problem-solving. Therefore, effective inclusive service delivery has multiple dimensions and cannot be reduced to mere physical placement of pupils with disabilities within mainstream classrooms.

Despite increasing advocacy for inclusive education in Nigeria, there remains limited empirical investigation into how teachers' attitude and competence jointly determine the quality of inclusive service delivery, particularly in Cross River State. Most existing studies tend to examine either attitude or competence in isolation, without exploring their combined predictive power. Furthermore, state-specific contextual realities, including resource constraints, teacher qualification disparities, rural-urban differences, and institutional culture, necessitate localised empirical inquiry.

With the renewed commitment embodied in the National Policy on Inclusive Education (2023), there is an urgent need for evidence-based data to inform teacher preparation programs, policy refinement, and professional development interventions in Cross River State. Understanding whether and to what extent teachers' attitudes and competence influence inclusive service delivery will provide actionable insights for strengthening inclusive practices at the primary school level.

It is against this comprehensive conceptual, empirical, and policy backdrop that the present study investigates the contribution of teachers' attitudes and competence to inclusive service delivery

for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. By examining these variables, the study aims to contribute to the advancement of inclusive education research, inform state-level educational reforms, and enhance the quality of educational experiences for pupils with intellectual disabilities.

Statement of the problem

Despite the global promotion of inclusive education as a way to ensure fair access to quality schooling, Nigerian primary schools still find it difficult to practically implement inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disability. The policy framework established by the Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria, provides guidance for inclusive schooling; however, there is often a substantial gap between policy provisions and classroom practice.

In Cross River State, many primary school pupils with intellectual disabilities continue to encounter barriers to meaningful participation in learning due to inadequate instructional resources, limited specialist support, and environmental constraints. Teachers are central to the success of inclusive education, yet variations in teachers' attitudes and professional competence may influence the quality of inclusive service delivery.

Even though previous studies have examined teacher attitude or competence independently, limited empirical evidence exists on their relative contribution to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities within the study area. This gap creates uncertainty regarding the extent to which these teacher-related factors determine inclusive education outcomes. This study, therefore, investigates the contribution of teachers' attitudes and professional competence to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disability in primary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Objectives

Generally, the study investigated the contribution of teachers' attitudes and competence to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the influence of teachers' attitudes on inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities.
2. To examine the influence of teachers' professional competence on inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities.

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between teachers' attitude and their contributions to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant difference between teachers' professional competence and their contributions to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted a correlational survey research design. This design is appropriate because the study seeks to determine the predictive relationships between teachers' attitudes, teachers' competence, and inclusive service delivery without manipulating the study variables.

Area of the Study

Primary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria, served as the location for this study. Observed implementation challenges of inclusive education within the state, despite the National Policy on Inclusive Education provisions (Federal Ministry of Education, 2023), informed the choice of the area.

Population of the Study

The population comprised all 12,749 primary school teachers in public primary schools in Cross River State who teach pupils with special educational needs, including pupils with intellectual disabilities.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample comprised 1275 teachers spread across the three educational zones in the state. Researchers arbitrarily chose them for the study, selecting approximately 10% to guarantee sufficient teacher representation. Researchers employed multistage sampling procedures, which involved stratified sampling for grouping schools based on local government educational zones. Simple random sampling to select participating schools, and proportionate sampling to select teachers from each selected school.

Instrumentation

Researchers developed a structured questionnaire titled “Teachers’ Attitude, Competence and Inclusive Service Delivery Questionnaire (TACISDQ)” which was the instrument used for the collection of data.

The instrument consists of four sections: Section A: Demographic information of respondents, Section B: Teachers’ attitudes toward inclusive education, Section C: Teachers’ professional competence in inclusive service delivery, and Section D: Inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities. A 4-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree was used to measure the responses.

Validity of the Instrument

The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity by experts in special education and educational measurement and evaluation from the University of Calabar. The validation process ensured that items adequately measure teachers’ attitude, competence, and inclusive service delivery constructs.

Reliability of the Instrument

The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient. The reliability estimates for the instruments ranged from 0.81 to 0.87 was considered acceptable for the study.

Collection of Data

Permission was obtained from relevant school authorities, and ethical clearance was secured before data collection. The researchers and trained research assistants administered the questionnaires to respondents and retrieved them after completion.

Statistical analysis

Data were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, and the hypotheses were tested using simple regression analysis at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between teachers' attitude and their contributions to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State.

Table 1: Regression analysis showing the contribution of teachers' attitude to inclusive service delivery

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	R	R ²
Regression	127.152	1	127.152	18.563*	.000	.120	.014
Residual	8719.593	1273	6.850				
Total	8846.745	1274					

Predictor variable	Unstandardized coefficient		Std coeff	t-value	p-value
	B	Standard error			
Constant	30.946	.511		60.599*	.000
Teachers' attitude	-.123	.028	-.120	-4.309*	.000

*Significant at .05 level. $P < .05$

According to the results presented in Table 1, a weak positive correlation exists between teachers' attitudes and inclusive service delivery, as indicated by the R-value of 0.120. This means that as teachers' attitudes become more positive, inclusive service delivery also tends to improve. However, the weak correlation as reflected in the R² and adjusted R² value of 0.014 respectively indicates that teachers' attitudes account for 1.4% of the variation in inclusive service delivery, meaning that other factors which are not accounted for in the present study contributed to the remaining 98.6% of the variation in inclusive service delivery.

Nevertheless, the p-value connected to the computed $F_{(1,1273)}$ value of 18.563 was found to be less than 0.05, signifying that the results are statistically significant and the null hypothesis should be rejected. Therefore, there is sufficient evidence to conclude that teachers' attitudes have a significant impact on inclusive service delivery in Cross River State and that this result was not obtained by chance. The regression constant of 30.946 indicates that the average inclusive service delivery score for teachers with the most negative attitudes is 30.946. The regression coefficient of -.123 indicates that for every one-unit increase in teachers' positive attitudes, there is a .123 unit increase in inclusive service delivery scores.

This result suggests that teachers' attitudes can play an important role in improving inclusive service delivery. By implication, this means that while the contribution of teachers' attitudes to inclusive service delivery is relatively small, it is still statistically significant. The results indicate that teachers' attitude plays a vital role in promoting inclusive education in Cross River State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between teachers' professional competence and their contributions to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State.

Table 2: Regression analysis showing the contribution of teachers' competence to inclusive service delivery

Source of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-value	p-value	R	R ²
Regression	2.935	1	2.935	.422*	.516	.018	.000
Residual	8843.810	1273	6.947				
Total	8846.745	1274					

Predictor variable	Unstandardized coefficient		Stdcoeff	t-value	p-value
	B	Standard error			
Constant	28.341	.662		42.811*	.000
Teachers' competence	.024	.037	.018	.650*	.516

*Significant at .05 level. $P < .05$

The findings presented in Table 2 indicate that there is a very weak positive correlation between teachers' competence and inclusive service delivery, as reflected in the R-value of 0.018. The R-squared value of 0.000 and the adjusted R-squared value of 0.000 suggest that the variation in teachers' competence did not have any significant influence on inclusive service delivery in Cross River State. Teachers' competence accounted for 0% of the total variation in inclusive service delivery.

The p-value related to the computed F-value of 0.422 was found to be greater than the acceptable standard of 0.05, which means that the results are not statistically significant, and the researcher retain the null hypothesis.

Hence, the null hypothesis was retained while the alternate hypothesis was rejected, meaning that there is not enough evidence to conclude that teachers' competence has a significant contribution to inclusive service delivery in Cross River State. The regression constant of 28.341 indicates that the average inclusive service delivery score for teachers with the lowest competence is 28.341. The regression coefficient of .024 means that in every one-unit increase in teachers' competence, there is a .02 unit increase in inclusive service delivery scores, suggesting that teachers' competence may not play a significant role in improving inclusive service delivery. While this finding may seem counterintuitive, it is important to note that this does not mean that competence is not important for teachers. It simply means that in the context of inclusive education in Cross River State, other factors may have a greater influence on inclusive service delivery.

Discussion

The findings in hypothesis one indicated that the contribution of teachers' attitudes to inclusive service delivery is weak. This finding suggests that extra elements may have played a role in the provision of inclusive services. For example, adequate training and support for teachers on inclusive education, availability of resources and materials, and administrative support may also influence the provision of inclusive services. It is also worth noting that teachers with more positive attitudes towards inclusive education are expected to provide better inclusive service delivery.

This result is in alignment with the results of Ugo and Yakwal (2017), who found that primary school teachers' attitudes to inclusive education for learners with visual impairment were negative. Thus, they concluded that teachers who are negative towards pupils with intellectual disabilities would not be patient enough with them in class. Chaudhary (2016) establishes that teachers with positive attitudes to inclusive education are inclined to perform better, which aligns with the results of the current research.

This finding also aligns with that of Dukmark (2013), who found that, generally, teachers show a positive attitude to educational inclusion; however, male teachers exhibited a more positive attitude than female teachers. Similarly, numerous studies have tried to recognise key areas of practical knowledge and skills that add to positive attitudes in inclusive practice (Odo, 2020). "Teacher preparation programs that focus on theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, and attitude change in inclusive education are helpful tools for newly certified teachers. In turn, this has a positive impact on learners with special educational needs" (Odo, 2020).

The results of the second hypothesis suggest that teachers' competencies do not significantly contribute to the inclusive service delivery of pupils with intellectual disabilities in the study area. This research finding is interesting and somewhat surprising. One would think that teachers with more knowledge and skills in special education would be better competent to provide effective inclusive service delivery for all learners, including those with intellectual disabilities. However, the research findings suggest that this is not always the case. It is essential to recognise that teacher competence encompasses the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that teachers possess to teach and effectively address diverse learning needs. In the context of inclusive education, teachers' competence includes the ability to design and implement individualised education plans, identify and tackle difficulties in learning, and

encourage social inclusion among learners with diverse needs.

Therefore, there are a few possible explanations for this finding. First, it is possible that the teachers in the study were already fairly competent in providing inclusive service delivery, even if they did not have specific training on intellectual disabilities. Second, it is possible that other factors, such as school resources and the needs of the learners, played a more prominent role in determining the quality of inclusive service delivery than the competence of the teachers. Third, it is also possible that the research methods used in the study were not sensitive enough to detect the effects of their competence on inclusive service delivery.

The research findings also suggest that inadequate school resources, such as insufficient funding, a lack of assistive technology, and limited access to specialist support, can make it difficult for teachers to provide effective inclusive education services. Similarly, inadequate administrative support, such as a lack of leadership, unclear policies, and ineffective monitoring and evaluation systems, can also hinder the provision of inclusive services by a competent teacher. Negative attitudes towards pupils with intellectual disabilities may result in stigmatisation and exclusion, making it difficult for teachers to provide inclusive services.

Despite the research findings, teachers need to have a basic understanding of special education, including the handling and management of pupils with intellectual disabilities. This knowledge can help teachers understand the needs of children with intellectual disabilities and develop more effective teaching strategies. Furthermore, teachers should be supportive of inclusive education and be willing to adapt their teaching methods to meet the needs of all students.

This result disagrees with that of Abba and Rashid (2020), who discovered that the motivation, methodological, and evaluation competence of teachers had a strong influence on the implementation of the inclusive education curriculum. Durdukoca (2021) also found that the professional competencies of participating teachers regarding inclusive education are at a high level. Same with Bariu, Chun, & Boudouaia (2022), who found that teachers' level of professional competencies significantly influences the implementation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in university classrooms.

Conclusion

In summary, the study's results reveal a complex relationship between teachers' efficacy in delivering inclusive services and their attitudes and competencies. Although it was found that teachers' attitudes contributed only minimally, this does not entirely diminish its importance. Previous research has demonstrated that positive attitudes towards inclusive education consistently enhance service delivery (Chaudhary, 2016; Dukmark, 2013). The modest correlation may suggest that attitudes alone cannot be translated into effective practice without additional factors such as administrative support, professional development, and resource availability. Therefore, improving teacher attitudes by itself may not lead to significant progress unless accompanied by structural and institutional changes.

Despite the outcome of the analysis of hypothesis 2, this study concludes that teachers' attitudes contribute to inclusive service delivery for pupils with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Cross River State. Teachers play a vital role in the overall success of any educational programme, including inclusive service delivery.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should be supportive of inclusive education and be willing to adapt their teaching methods to meet the needs of all students.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to show a more positive attitude towards the inclusion of pupils with intellectual disabilities.
3. Teachers should be allowed to improve their skills in special needs through attending special needs conferences, seminars, and workshops of stakeholders for effective inclusive services.

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